

MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF BARIUM ZIRCONATE COATED ALUMINA FIBER/ALUMINA MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Barium zirconate (BaZrO_3) is a candidate material for interface engineering of alumina fiber/alumina matrix composites. Conventional wisdom has it that an interfacial coating should not react chemically with either the fiber or the matrix. The novelty of our approach is in-situ development of multiple interphase layers as the result of chemical reactions between BaZrO_3 and Al_2O_3 at temperatures above 1300°C during processing. These interphase layers are weak enough to cause crack deflection and hence likely to increase toughness of the composite.

In this work, Nextel 610 fiber tows and fabric (3M Co.) was used as reinforcement and high purity (over 99.99% pure) submicrometer alumina powder (Baikowski Inter. Co.) is used as matrix material. A barium zirconate coating was synthesized by sol-gel technique. Desized fiber tows or fabric pieces were arranged in alumina powder inside a graphite die and the composite was fabricated by unidirectional hot pressing. Characterization of the reaction products was carried out by SEM, EDS, and X-ray diffraction techniques. It was found that reaction products included ZrO_2 and Ba- β aluminates such as $\text{BaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{BaO}\cdot 7.3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. In indentation crack studies and three point bend tests, it was found that ZrO_2 layer served as a weak interface for crack deflection.

Also, $\text{BaO}\cdot 7.3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ has an anisotropic oxide layered structure, which should be capable of easy cleavage along basal planes aligned parallel with the interface, thus improving fracture toughness of the composite. The composite showed an increased toughness compared to that of monolithic alumina when tested in three-point bend. This composite has also shown good thermal cycling resistance when cycled between room temperature and 1000°C . We found no significant change in modulus and density of the composite after thermal cycling.

KEYWORDS: Ceramic matrix composite, oxide, fiber, matrix, interface.

INTRODUCTION

The development of new advanced structural materials for high temperature application remains an important technological goal. They are required to bear high stresses at temperatures over 1000°C , perform without changes in their properties for hundreds of hours, withstand highly reactive and hostile environments and have adequate fracture toughness and damage tolerance in the entire temperature range, from ambient temperature to service conditions [1-3]. A great deal of work has been done in understanding ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) reinforced with continuous fibers with an increasing focus on the role of the fiber/matrix interface. CMCs are being developed to overcome the intrinsic brittleness of monolithic ceramics with the aim of being introduced in structural parts used in severe environments. The potential applications of CMCs include rocket and jet engines, gas turbines for power plants, heat shields for space vehicles, fusion reactor first wall, aircraft brakes, heat treatment furnaces, wear resistant parts, etc [2]. The use of light CMCs in place of heavy superalloys is expected to yield

significant weight saving and also will allow an increase of the temperature at which the engine can be operated [4].

Many applications of CMCs involve air as an environment, therefore, oxide/oxide CMCs are being explored, since they are inherently oxidation resistant and thermally stable. Examples of oxide/oxide include, alumina fiber/alumina matrix composites or mullite fiber/mullite matrix composites [2]. However, in case of the oxide/oxide CMCs, while processing, a strong chemical bond is formed at the fiber/matrix interface and in turn the composite behaves like a monolith. Hence, interface tailoring is essential at the fiber/matrix interface, which helps in fiber debonding and fiber pullout. In case of the continuous fiber reinforced composites, fiber debonding and fiber pullout are the most important energy consuming mechanisms during the failure of the composite. Thus, interface tailoring helps making the composite tougher.

Barium zirconate, BaZrO_3 , is a candidate material for interfacial coating for alumina fiber/alumina matrix composites [5]. Conventionally, it was thought that there should not be any chemical reaction between fiber/coating or matrix/interface interface, as in alumina/lanthanum phosphate/alumina or alumina/tin oxide/alumina composites. The novel approach of our work is the development of *in situ* multiple interphase layers during the processing of $\text{BaZrO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ composites [6, 7]. It was shown that in spite of chemical reactions, sharp interfaces form and some of the interfaces are weak enough to allow fiber/matrix debonding and crack deflection.

Schematically, the composite can be illustrated as shown in Fig. 1. In this, during processing, $\text{BaZrO}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ react to form ZrO_2 and barium aluminates such as $\text{BaO}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{BaO}\cdot 7.3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ [8].

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of (a) the diffusional process leading to the reaction layers (b) the formation of reaction products between BaZrO_3 and Al_2O_3 (from ref. [8])

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

Reinforcement: The Reinforcement used was Nextel 610 fiber tows and fabric (3M corp., MN). Nextel 610 fiber tows consist of polycrystalline α -alumina fibers. In one tow there are approximately 400-450 fibers. The diameter of single fibers ranged between 12-15 μm . A coating usually called “size” is applied by the manufacturer on the fibers to protect them from any damage during handling.

Matrix: Alumina matrix powder of over 99.99% purity and having an average particle size of 1 μm (Baikowski Inter. Corp., NC) was first ball milled for 24 hours, using high-purity alumina balls to get very fine particle size. For ball milling of the powder, a slurry was prepared in water having a pH of 4. The resulting slurry was dried and fine powder of alumina was obtained.

Interphase: Barium zirconate precursor was used as an interphase material, which was processed using sol-gel technique. It was synthesized by using barium acetate powder and zirconium-n-propoxide. The barium acetate was first dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid and methanol at 70°C while the mixture was continuously stirred. It was followed by the addition of N-propanol ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) containing 70% Zr-n-propoxide ($\text{Zr}[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CH}_3]_4$). The solution was dried on a hot plate until dry gel was obtained. The gel was rehydrated with a measured quantity of distilled water to obtain barium zirconate sol.

Experimental Procedure

Fabrication of the composite: Fibers were desized prior to coating by heating them upto 800 °C. Fibers are coated with BaZrO_3 sol. After coating, fibers were calcined at around 1000 °C. The composite was fabricated by uniaxial hot pressing. Alumina powder and BaZrO_3 coated fibers were arranged in layers in the graphite die. A graphite die was first coated with BN and then lined with a layer of grafoil and molybdenum sheet to avoid carbon diffusion into the composite. BN coating was applied on the molybdenum sheet for ease of removal of the composite after hot pressing. Hot pressing was done under vacuum at 1300-1400°C for about 90 minutes. Pressure applied during hot pressing was 35 MPa (5000 psi). Heating and cooling rates were 15°C/minute and 50°C/minute, respectively.

Characterization: Microstructural characterization was performed by optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Moreover, the crack propagation paths and interaction of cracks with the interfaces were examined by optical microscopy and SEM observation of the indented surfaces obtained a with Vickers indenter. Samples were sputter coated with Au-Pd prior to examination in SEM. Young's modulus was measured by impulse excitation, a nondestructive inspection technique [9].

Testing of the Composite

Indentation cracking: Samples used for this study contained unidirectional Nextel 610 fiber tows coated with barium zirconate. Standard metallographic preparation was done to obtain polished cross sections. The mounted samples were indented by Vickers microindentation under 1 kg loads and examined using an optical microscope. The crack path was observed using optical microscope and SEM.

Thermal cycling: Samples containing Nextel fabric, in which the fibers were arranged in 90° and 0° and contain 20 volume % of fibers were subjected to thermal cycling. Sample dimensions were 3.98 x 5.35 x 29.61 mm. The thermal cycling apparatus used in this study is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of an automated, computer controlled pneumatic piston that inserts the sample into a tube furnace for a preset time, and then withdraws it. After withdrawal, the sample was cooled by an electric fan [10]. After fixed intervals of cycles, elastic modulus and density of the samples were measured. Samples were cycled for 15 minutes between room temperature and 1000°C and forced air cooled for 5 minutes. The temperature was measured on the sample surface with a thermocouple.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of the thermal cycling apparatus (after ref. 10)

Thermal shock studies: An indentation-quench test was used to evaluate the thermal shock resistance of the composite [11,12]. In this test, precracks were made in the center of the sample to avoid any edge effects and the increase in the crack length was measured after thermal shock. Composite samples containing Nextel fabric, with fibers arranged in 90° and 0° and about 20 volume % of fibers were used. Samples have their four larger faces polished and Young's modulus of each sample was measured before thermal shock. Precracks were made through indentation with a Vickers diamond indenter. The peak load applied was 10 N for 35 seconds. The residual stresses generated during indentation and polishing were removed by further annealing of the samples at 800°C for 4 hours. The length of the surface crack, c , was measured from the center of the indentation by optical microscopy. The specimens were heated in a furnace with air atmosphere and then quenched by free fall into water at room temperature. Five samples were tested with temperature differences ranging from 200 to 600°C . The specimens were kept in the furnace for approximately 20 minutes to ensure temperature uniformity before quenching. There was no measurable change in the temperature of water after quenching. Young's modulus of each sample was measured after the quenching and the samples were examined for any surface cracks due to thermal stresses generated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crack Propagation Studies: The crack propagation paths were observed under the SEM. It was found that cracks often either stopped or were deflected at the interface. The crack was mainly seen to be deflected at the interface of ZrO_2 (seen as white region in SEM) and barium aluminate compounds (seen as gray region in SEM) as shown in Fig.3. As seen in a higher magnification picture in Fig. 4, the interface looked very rough and the crack propagated in a zigzag fashion. Reaction zones consisting of barium aluminate compounds (seen as gray region in Fig.3) were seen to penetrate the matrix as well as the fibers and crack deflection or blunting was observed at both sets of interfaces.

Figure 3 Interaction of a crack with the coating. Note the crack following the coating. M and F represent matrix and fiber respectively.

Figure 4 Interaction of crack with the interface. The crack deflects at the interface due to fiber debonding. M and F represent matrix and fiber respectively.

Thermal Cycling: In general, in composite materials, there exists difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the fiber and the matrix. This incompatibility leads to thermal stresses when there is a temperature change [1, 10]. Young's modulus of the sample in flexure was measured to be 357 GPa and the density was found to be 97% of theoretical density. After cycling modulus was 352 GPa and thus no significant change in composite modulus was observed after 1300 cycles. Also the density of the composite remained unchanged after cycling.

In the composite system under investigation, the CTE difference in the composite arises from the reaction products developed during the reaction between the coating and the fiber and matrix. The complex structure of these reaction products was explained earlier. Among the reaction products, ZrO_2 (with a CTE value $10.0 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$) has a CTE very close to that of Al_2O_3 (with a CTE value $8.5 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$). So again, the residual stresses generated are not very significant. Since very little damage was found, it can be hypothesized that the CTE of β -alumina compounds may also be very close to that of alumina and zirconia.

Thermal Shock: In thermal shock studies, we found that samples quenched from 600, 500, 400 and 300 $^\circ C$ showed extensive cracking of matrix and also the precracks had grown in each case. These cracks either stopped or deflected at the fiber/matrix interfaces and propagated in a zigzag manner through the fiber tows as seen in Fig. 4. It was difficult to measure the crack lengths after quenching, since there was no clear distinction between the growth of matrix cracks and indentation cracks. The sample quenched from 200 $^\circ C$ had growth of the precracks, but did not show initiation of other matrix cracks. The precracks grown stopped at the fiber/matrix interface. From this we estimate that critical temperature for thermal shock sensitivity for these composites is between 200 – 300 $^\circ C$, which is an improvement over that of monolithic alumina

In this system, the thermal stresses generated are due to steep thermal gradient between surface and the inside of the sample owing to low thermal conductivity of alumina. There was a dramatic change in the modulus of the composite after thermal shock. The Young's modulus changed from an initial value of 358 GPa to a value of 135 GPa after thermal shock.

Figure 4 Indentation crack traveling in a zigzag manner through the fiber tows when the composite is quenched from 600 °C

CONCLUSIONS

Barium zirconate coated alumina fibers were incorporated in an alumina matrix by hot pressing. During processing, in situ reaction interphase layers of ZrO_2 , $BaO \cdot Al_2O_3$ and $BaO \cdot 7.3Al_2O_3$ developed. Crack propagation studies showed that these new interfaces were weak enough to deflect cracks around the fibers. This is likely to lead to fiber debonding and thus increase the toughness of the composite.

The composite showed good thermal cycling resistance when cycled between room temperature and 1000°C. In thermal shock studies, the cracks generated due to thermal stresses either stopped at the interface or propagated in a zigzag manner through the fiber tows owing to fiber debonding at the fiber/matrix interface.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K.K. Chawla, Ceramic Matrix Composites, second edition, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Boston, 2003.
- [2] K.K. Chawla, C. Coffin, Z.R. Xu, International Materials reviews (2000) **45** 165-189.
- [3] A. G. Evans, Journal of American Ceramic Society (1990) **73** 187-206.

- [4] L.C. Lev, A.S. Argon, *Materials Science and Engineering* (1995) **A195** 251-261.
- [5] G.M. Gladysz, M. Schmucker, K.K. Chawla, H. Schneider, D.L. Joslin, M.K. Ferber, *Materials Characterization* (1998) **45** 209-214.
- [6] G.M. Gladysz, K.K. Chawla, *Composites: Part A* (2001) **32** 173-178.
- [7] M. Koopman, S. Duncan, K.K. Chawla, C. Coffin, *Composites: Part A* (2001) **32** 1039-1044.
- [8] Z. Chen, S. Duncan, K.K. Chawla, M. Koopman, G.M. Janowski, *Materials Characterization* (2002), **48** 305-314.
- [9] ASTM designation, E 1876 – 99, *Annual book of ASTM standards* (1999) 1-15.
- [10] N. Chawla, K.K. Chawla, M. Koopman, B. Patel, C. Coffin, J.I. Eldridge, *Composite Science and Technology*, (2001) **61** 1923-1930.
- [11] G.A. Schneider, G. Petzow, *Thermal shock and thermal fatigue behavior of advanced ceramics*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1993.
- [12] N.C. Biswas, S.P. Chaudhuri, *Ceramics International*, (1997) **23** 69-72.